

Investigating the Inactivation Efficacy of SDBD Plasma Generated in Contact with Water for Bacterial Deactivation and Biofilm Control

Oleksandr Galmiz¹, Bernard Gitura Kimani¹, Ramin Mehrabifard¹ and Zdenko Machala¹

¹Division of Environmental Physics, Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics, Comenius University in Bratislava, Mlynská dolina, 842 48 Bratislava, Slovakia

E-mail: oleksandr.galmiz@uniba.sk

This study investigates the potential of plasma technology for inactivating planktonic and sessile modes of microbial growth. This technique utilizes a water solution as a discharge electrode, allowing for the integration of water discharges and surface dielectric barrier discharges (SDBD) [1]. The SDBD originates at the interface between the liquid electrode, surrounding air, and a dielectric material (often a tube). This unique combination offers several advantages.

Firstly, it enables the generation of highly oxidative plasma in direct contact with the liquid. This characteristic translates to a remarkable ability to uniformly treat the inner surfaces of polymer hollow objects, such as tubes and catheters, with plasma [2].

Our research aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of this plasma technology in inactivating bacteria through two distinct approaches: direct plasma treatment of contaminated liquid and plasma treatment of biofilms on polymer tubes.

In the first approach, the study examined the impact of plasma on a solution contaminated with planktonic *E. coli* CCM 3954. This contaminated solution was strategically employed as one of the liquid electrodes, facilitating direct contact between the plasma and the bacterial population. We explored the effects of various, yet reasonable, power levels and treatment durations on the viability of the studied microorganisms.

The second approach focused on evaluating the effect of plasma treatment on pre-established *E. coli* biofilms adhered to the inner surface of polymeric tubes. To achieve this, a plasma ring was ignited at the bottom of the tube and then moved along the entire length of the tube. This approach simulates a practical application scenario where the plasma treatment would need to address biofilms formed on the inner surfaces of medical devices such as catheters. The study investigated the influence of several key factors, including the input power level, the speed at which the plasma ring was moved along the tube, and the duration of biofilm cultivation prior to treatment.

Our research results demonstrate that plasma treatment is a viable method for reducing microbial contamination within the water and decreasing the overall biomass of mature biofilms established on the inner surfaces of polymer tubes. These findings suggest that plasma technology holds promise as a novel and effective approach for disinfection and biofilm control in various applications, particularly those involving medical devices and water treatment.

Acknowledgment: This work was supported by Marie S. Curie Action Postdoctoral Fellowship under Horizon Europe with grant agreement number 101066764 and Slovak Research and Development Agency APVV-22-0247.

References

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